

Graphical Abstract

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Highlights

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- An adaptive optimal model-free solution is proposed to control solar collector fields
- The Reinforcement Q-learning algorithm is applied in a validated solar thermal plant
- It is demonstrated that Q-learning algorithm converges to optimal gains
- The model-free controller overcomes parameter-varying issues of model based approaches

Optimal model-free control based on reinforcement Q-learning for solar collector fields

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Abstract

Controlling solar collector fields is challenging in what concerns the development of representative models and adequate control solutions. To face this issue, this work proposes an adaptive optimal model free-controller based on the Reinforcement Q-learning algorithm. The proposed solution requires only the measurement of the plant information, such as working fluid temperature and flow rate, and the reference trajectory to provide an optimal control law that converges to the optimal gains of a Linear Quadratic Tracking (LQT) controller. The Q-learning algorithm is employed to control a validated solar collector field model of the CIESOL thermal plant (Almería, Spain) in a trustworthy simulated scenario considering actual data from the facility. For the sake of comparison, the Q-learning algorithm is compared to the conventional LQT controller. The results demonstrate the effectiveness and advantages of the model-free controller, in which the Q-learning algorithm can overcome the significant issues of model-based controllers in solar collector fields, such as adapting the control law, effortlessly managing time-varying parameter system, and simplifying the control strategy implementation. The Q-Learning solution presented a better performance in the

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sunny day scenario when slight variations of solar irradiance occur, achieving less than 15% mean error of the computed optimal gains during the entire simulation. The proposed model-free strategy shows to be extended appropriately to different systems without changing the controller formulation, being valuable for handling actual applications.

Keywords: Reinforcement Learning, Q-learning, Optimal Control, Solar plant

1. Introduction

Renewable energy has been recognized worldwide as the major solution to face the transition from fossil fuels to sustainable energy sources (Li and Huang, 2020). Over the last twenty years, alternative energy and technology resources have been the focus of investigations to address the global concern about greenhouse gas emissions and climate change (Martín, 2022). Engaging and successful solutions, such as biomass, hydroelectric, ocean, and wind energy sources, are a reality that contributes to altering the global energy matrix. In this context, among the various potential alternatives, solar energy plays a crucial role as an abundant and promising energy source, prospecting to reach 27% of the global electricity generation by 2050 (Abdelrazik et al., 2022; Sikiru et al., 2022; Heffron et al., 2021).

Solar energy can be mainly harnessed by handling two techniques: photovoltaic (PV) panels, which directly convert the solar irradiance into electric energy, and solar thermal plants, in which optical elements reflect and concentrate the solar irradiance and, hence, deliver thermal energy to a specific heat transfer fluid (HTF). Regarding solar thermal plants, the solar collector field (SCF) system is the primary component that determines the overall plant's efficiency. In fact, by appropriately managing the HTF outlet temperature, the working fluid can correctly deliver the necessary thermal energy to a demand system (Gallego et al., 2022; Badal et al., 2019). Nevertheless, controlling this system turns out to be very challenging from an automatic control perspective since SCFs are presented as a nonlinear and multidisturbed process (Camacho et al., 2012; Camacho and Gallego, 2013).

Comprehensive endeavors in the automatic control field have been reported in the literature to offer suitable and efficient solutions to control SCF systems (Pataro et al., 2022b; Bejarano et al., 2020; de Araújo Elias et al., 2019; Gil et al., 2018; Elmetennani and Laleg-Kirati, 2017; Lemos et al., 2014;

Torrico et al., 2010; Cirre et al., 2010; Camacho et al., 2007). The control solutions are developed considering the SCF dynamics that dictate the HTF temperature evolution as a function of the systems inputs, such as ambient and inlet temperature, solar irradiance, and HTF flow rate. The system dynamics are studied mainly by assuming data-driven or first-principles models (Tian et al., 2018; Bava and Furbo, 2017; Deng et al., 2015). Nevertheless, a compromise relation inevitably arises from the control solution formulations: simple models versus control performance. By selecting straightforward representations, for instance, First Order plus Dead Time (FOPDT) model, the system’s dynamics are only partially captured due to the SCF nonlinearity, and, thus, the control solution tends to lose performance. On the other hand, high-fidelity models are particularly complex to be formulated and require advanced control approaches with elevated computational costs. In addition, it also translates into demanding specialized control engineers to develop and adequately implement the strategy in existing systems. Therefore, a proper control strategy combined to the process model is always a challenging concern for the control of SCFs.

In the recent literature, a promising solution to deal with complexity model-based controllers (MBC) for SCFs is known as model-free control, or also so-called data-driven control (DDC) (Hou and Wang, 2013). Essentially, DDCs are those control strategies that use only data measured on the system to be controlled without using any model during the controller adaptation (Heusden, 2010; Helvoort, 2007). Hence, the synthesis of DDC lies only in the system input-output measurements, either assuming a pre-specified or unknown control structure. The benefits of using DDCs approaches instead of MBCs for SCF lie in three aspects: first, DDCs frameworks overcome the necessity of the SCF model, which reduces several problems of the system modeling and control strategies complexity; secondly, unmodeled dynamics and uncertainty issues of MBC for SCF systems do not appear in the DDCs since the solution uses the system data that embeds those issues entirely; finally, the challenges of time-varying parameters in MBCs disappear in DDC methods due to the fact that in the input-output data level this effect is irrelevant. Despite these advantages, model-free controllers are still in the early stage of development, even though several contributions encourages the investigation of this approach in SCF systems (Chang et al., 2011; Lu et al., 2011; Hou and Jin, 2011; van Helvoort et al., 2008; Spall and Cristion, 1998).

Regarding DDC pre-specified control structure strategy, the Q-Learning algorithm stands out as a solution to obtain an optimal control law using the

system input-output data. The Q-learning method arises from the necessity of excusing the use of the system model for the Reinforcement Learning (RL) formulation (Watkins, 1989). As reviewed in Lewis and Vrabie (2009), the RL technique can be referred to as an adaptive control method, in which information collected from the system is used to adapt the control law that converges to optimal solution of the Linear-Quadratic Regulator (LQR). Hence, the Q-learning algorithm is employed to approximate the dynamic inversion concept (which requires the system’s models knowledge) using only the plant inputs and state values to obtain the LQR optimal control. Although meaningful works have addressed in RL and Q-learning algorithms for solar system energy management (Heidari et al., 2022; Bendevis et al., 2020; Correa-Jullian et al., 2020; Bara et al., 2017; Raju et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2014; Leo et al., 2014; Kuznetsova et al., 2013), controlling SCF using model-free solutions is still an open field in the literature.

Bearing all that in mind, this work presents an optimal model-free control solution as an alternative to solve the impasse of complex modeling and controller approaches currently applied in SCF systems. The Q-learning algorithm is proposed as the pre-specified DDC structure in which the SCF outlet temperature (state) and HTF flow rate (input) information are used to adapt the optimal gains of the control strategy. Moreover, herein, the Q-learning method is formulated considering an incremental form of the input, which is appropriate to eliminate steady-state errors commonly found in reference tracking scenarios. The Q-learning algorithm is employed in a trustworthy simulated environment using validated models with time-varying parameters and actual data from the solar thermal plant located in CIESOL (University of Almería, Spain) to demonstrate the control capabilities. In this scenario, the proposed solution is compared to a Linear-Quadratic Tracking (LQT) controller, aiming to illustrate the advantages of each strategy with similar control performances.

The contributions of this work are grounded on three main aspects:

- a combined adaptive optimal and model-free solution is proposed for SCF systems, aiming to address the system’s nonlinearity and time-varying parameter in an unique solution.
- the proposal is effectively valuable for the SCF at the operational level, resulting in a plug-and-play control structure that can be used in real systems without requiring any prior engineering knowledge for imple-

mentation, being, in addition, easily extensible to different solar thermal installations;

- although reliable SCF models are available in the literature, the model-free controller overcomes serious MBC issues, such as i) uncertainties of system structure are problematic to manage, ii) control performance using MBC deteriorates when applied to different SCF systems for which it was not designed, iii) the complexity of SCF mathematical model can be challenging to design MBC strategies.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the CIESOL solar thermal facility used as case study. Section 3 details the Q-learning algorithm's design based on the the RL formulation for the inputs' incremental form. Section 4 illustrates the results of the simulated scenario, comparing the Q-learning with the LQT strategy. Finally, Section 5 reports the final considerations.

2. CIESOL thermal plant

This section presents the solar thermal plant used as case study for the application of the Q-learning algorithm. Thus, the CIESOL facility (Fig. 1) is described, focusing on the SCF system and the subsystems that compose the plant.

Figure 1: CIESOL flat-plate SCF located at University of Almería, Spain.

The solar thermal system of CIESOL uses the SCF as a primary energy source to produce hot water for the load system. The entire plant configuration can be divided into the primary circuit, which aims at collecting and storing thermal energy, and the secondary circuit, defined as the load demand circuit. For the purposes of this work, only the primary circuit is considered since it is the stage that comprises the SCF. Figure 2 details the primary circuit configuration.

Figure 2: CIESOL primary circuit.

2.1. Solar collector field

The SCF system comprises 80 flat-plate solar collectors, divided into ten rows of eight parallel collectors each, with a total surface of 160.2 m^2 , oriented in the south direction. The designed collectors temperature range is from $-20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. However, concerning the load demand, the HTF operating temperature can vary from 70 to $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The validated model of the SCF used for the simulation results is detailed in Appendix A.

With the focus of detailing the effectiveness of the Q-learning algorithm in dealing with time-varying parameter models, in this work, the heat thermal losses variation is considered. As demonstrated in Camacho et al. (2012), the heat loss parameter of the SCF varies linearly as a function of the collector’s mean temperature. Therefore, a linear parameter varying design is proposed to consider the time-varying parameter H_n during the simulation of the Q-learning algorithm (see Eq. (A.1)). The linear variation around $\pm 50\%$ of the nominal value H_n is defined in this case study as

$$H(T_{col}(t)) = H_n \left((1 - c) + (2c) \frac{T_{col}(t) - T_{max}}{T_{min} - T_{max}} \right), \quad (1)$$

where $T_{col}(t)$ is the difference in temperature between the mean inlet and outlet temperature and the ambient temperature

$$T_{col}(t) = \frac{T_{sc,o}(t) + T_{sc,in}(t - d_{T_{in}})}{2} - T_a(t) \quad (2)$$

$c = -0.5$, and $T_{max} = 45$ [°C] and $T_{min} = 25$ [°C] are the maximum and minimum mean temperature of the collectors, respectively, obtained after several simulated scenarios using the validated model and actual data of the CIESOL facility.

2.2. Accumulation tanks

The storage system comprises two accumulation tanks connected in series with a capacity of 5000 L each. The primary tank’s goal is to store heat energy as hot water, and, secondarily, warm up the primary circuit water before the operation starts. Regarding overall operational benefits, by using the accumulation tanks, the temperature oscillations that occur in the SCF are filtered, and smooth variations of the HTF temperature arrive at the load demand system. Furthermore, in what concerns the SCF control, the tanks can also accommodate the water flow variations and avoid resonance phenomena in the SCF due to the return of the HTF fluid as the inlet fluid in the collectors.

The proposed validated model of the accumulation tanks is detailed in Pataro et al. (2022a).

2.3. Absorption chiller

The absorption chiller acts as the demand system of the CIESOL facility. This system interconnects the primary and secondary circuits, composed

of the Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) components of the inside rooms of the building. This system is operated to ensure the refrigeration of the CIESOL building rooms, in which the absorption chiller is powered by the SCF associated with the two accumulation tanks as depicted in Fig. 2. The validated first principle model of the CIESOL absorption chiller model Yazaki WFC SC 20 is represented in Pataro et al. (2022c).

Therefore, based on the proposed validated models of the CIESOL facility, the model-free Q-learning controller can be developed for a trustworthy simulation of the presented solar plant.

3. Q-learning algorithm

In this section, the Q-learning algorithm is designed considering the RL procedure for an incremental form of the inputs. This formulation allows for eliminating the steady-state error with small magnitudes of the tuning parameters. The solution is compared to the Q-learning method for reference tracking proposed in Kiumarsi et al. (2014), aiming at demonstrating the effectiveness of the modified design.

3.1. Reinforcement learning development

Before presenting the Q-learning algorithm, first, a modified RL algorithm is formulated for output reference tracking without steady-state error. The procedure follows the results developed in Kiumarsi et al. (2014). First, consider an augmented state-space model for the incremental form of the inputs in discrete-time k :

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_{k+1} \\ \mathbf{u}_{k+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_0 & \mathbf{B}_0 \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_k \\ \mathbf{u}_k \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{u}_k, \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{y}_k = [\mathbf{C}_0 \quad \mathbf{0}] \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_k \\ \mathbf{u}_k \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

in which matrices \mathbf{A}_0 , \mathbf{B}_0 , \mathbf{C}_0 are the state, input and output matrices of the original state-space representation, respectively, $\mathbf{0}$ is a zero matrix and \mathbf{I} is an identity matrix, with the compatible dimension of the system states and inputs. Moreover, $\mathbf{x}_k \in R^a$ is the measured state, $\mathbf{u}_k \in R^b$ is the control input, $\mathbf{y}_k \in R^c$ is the system output, and $\Delta \mathbf{u}_k = \mathbf{u}_{k+1} - \mathbf{u}_k$ is the increment of the input in one sample time. For the sake of simplicity, consider the

abuse of notation $\mathbb{X}_k = \mathbb{X}(k)$. Moreover, to take into account the reference tracking scenario, consider the reference command generator:

$$\mathbf{r}_{k+1} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{r}_k \quad (5)$$

wherein \mathbf{r}_k is the output desired value and \mathbf{F} is the command trajectory matrix. Hence, the final augmented state-space can be synthesized as :

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_{k+1} \\ \mathbf{u}_{k+1} \\ \mathbf{r}_{k+1} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{X}_{k+1}} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_0 & \mathbf{B}_0 & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{F} \end{bmatrix}}_{\bar{\mathbf{A}}} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_k \\ \mathbf{u}_k \\ \mathbf{r}_k \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{X}_k} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{I} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}}_{\bar{\mathbf{B}}} \Delta \mathbf{u}_k. \quad (6)$$

The LQT problem can be formulated as an infinite-horizon discounted value function such as

$$V(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{r}_k) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=k}^{\infty} \gamma^{i-k} [(\mathbf{C}_0 \mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{r}_i)^\top \mathbf{Q}_0 (\mathbf{C}_0 \mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{r}_i) + \Delta \mathbf{u}_i^\top \mathbf{R} \Delta \mathbf{u}_i], \quad (7)$$

in which, \mathbf{Q}_0 and \mathbf{R} are the weight tuning matrices for the output error and input increment movements, respectively, and $0 < \gamma < 1$ is the discount factor. Notice that, the term related to the output error can be defined as

$$\begin{aligned} & (\mathbf{C}_0 \mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{r}_i)^\top \mathbf{Q}_0 (\mathbf{C}_0 \mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{r}_i) = \\ & \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_i \\ \mathbf{u}_i \\ \mathbf{r}_i \end{bmatrix}^\top \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_0 & \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix}^\top \mathbf{Q}_0 \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_0 & \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_i \\ \mathbf{u}_i \\ \mathbf{r}_i \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Therefore, considering the proposed augmented states in Eq. (6), the value function in (7) is rewritten as

$$V(\mathbf{X}_k) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=k}^{\infty} \gamma^{i-k} [\mathbf{X}_i^\top \bar{\mathbf{Q}} \mathbf{X}_i + \Delta \mathbf{u}_i^\top \mathbf{R} \Delta \mathbf{u}_i], \quad (9)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{Q}} = \bar{\mathbf{C}}^\top \mathbf{Q}_0 \bar{\mathbf{C}}$, and $\bar{\mathbf{C}} = [\mathbf{C}_0 \quad \mathbf{0} \quad -\mathbf{I}]$.

Therefore, to develop the RL for the LQT infinite-horizon problem described in (9), it must be demonstrated that the proposed LQT problem can be solved using the Bellman equation. First, considering to formulate

the LQT problem as a quadratic function; and then, assuming that there is a stabilizing state feedback control law that depends on the states at each sampling time

$$\Delta \mathbf{u}_k = \mathbf{K}_x \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{K}_u \mathbf{u}_k + \mathbf{K}_r \mathbf{r}_k = \mathbf{K} \mathbf{X}_k. \quad (10)$$

Thus, by using the system model in Eq. (6) and the control law Eq. (10), the system evolution is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_{k+1} &= [\mathbf{A}_0 \ \mathbf{B}_0 \ \mathbf{0}] \mathbf{X}_k, \\ \mathbf{u}_{k+1} &= \mathbf{u}_k + \mathbf{K}_x \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{K}_u \mathbf{u}_k + \mathbf{K}_r \mathbf{r}_k = [\mathbf{K}_x \ (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{K}_u) \ \mathbf{K}_r] \mathbf{X}_k, \\ \mathbf{r}_{k+1} &= [\mathbf{0} \ \mathbf{0} \ \mathbf{F}] \mathbf{X}_k. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Eq. (11) is synthesized as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_{k+1} \\ \mathbf{u}_{k+1} \\ \mathbf{r}_{k+1} \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_0 & \mathbf{B}_0 & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{K}_x & (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{K}_u) & \mathbf{K}_r \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{F} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{G}} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_k \\ \mathbf{u}_k \\ \mathbf{r}_k \end{bmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

Substituting Eq. (12) and Eq.(10) in Eq. (9), the value function is reformulated as

$$\begin{aligned} V(\mathbf{X}_k) &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=k}^{\infty} \gamma^{i-k} \left[\mathbf{X}_i^\top \mathbf{G}^{i-k\top} \overline{\mathbf{Q}} \mathbf{G}^{i-k} \mathbf{X}_i + \mathbf{X}_i^\top \mathbf{K}^\top \mathbf{R} \mathbf{K} \mathbf{X}_i \right], \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \gamma^i \left[\mathbf{X}_k^\top \mathbf{G}^{i\top} \overline{\mathbf{Q}} \mathbf{G}^i \mathbf{X}_k + \mathbf{X}_k^\top \mathbf{K}^\top \mathbf{R} \mathbf{K} \mathbf{X}_k \right], \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Hence, assuming that the states at instant k are measured, the LQT solution can be written as a quadratic form of the augmented states

$$V(\mathbf{X}_k) = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{X}_k^\top \mathbf{P} \mathbf{X}_k, \quad (14)$$

in which $\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{P}^\top > 0$ is

$$\mathbf{P} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \gamma^i \left[\mathbf{G}^{i\top} \overline{\mathbf{Q}} \mathbf{G}^i + \mathbf{K}^\top \mathbf{R} \mathbf{K} \right]. \quad (15)$$

Considering this, and taking Eq. (14), one can define the Bellman equation for the proposed LQT problem as

$$\mathbf{X}_k^\top \mathbf{P} \mathbf{X}_k = \mathbf{X}_k^\top \bar{\mathbf{Q}} \mathbf{X}_k + \Delta \mathbf{u}_k^\top \mathbf{R} \Delta \mathbf{u}_k + \gamma V(\mathbf{x}_{k+1}). \quad (16)$$

Thus, the Hamiltonian equation for the LQT problem is presented

$$H(\mathbf{X}_k, \Delta \mathbf{u}_k) = \mathbf{X}_k^\top \bar{\mathbf{Q}} \mathbf{X}_k + \Delta \mathbf{u}_k^\top \mathbf{R} \Delta \mathbf{u}_k + \gamma V(\mathbf{x}_{k+1}) - V(\mathbf{x}_k). \quad (17)$$

By employing the Bellman principle (Bellman et al., 1957), the presented LQT problem can be solved, following the same results as the Algebraic Ricatti Equation (ARE) for the LQT tracking problem. Therefore, employing the stationary optimality conditions of the optimal problem with no input constraints

$$\frac{\partial H(\mathbf{X}_k, \Delta \mathbf{u}_k)}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{u}_k} = 2\mathbf{R} \Delta \mathbf{u}_k + 2\gamma \bar{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{P} (\bar{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{X}_k + \bar{\mathbf{B}} \Delta \mathbf{u}_k) = 0, \quad (18)$$

where the optimal control values is calculated as

$$\Delta \mathbf{u}_k = -(\mathbf{R} + \gamma \bar{\mathbf{B}}^\top \mathbf{P} \bar{\mathbf{B}})^{-1} \gamma \bar{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{P} \bar{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{X}_k. \quad (19)$$

Replacing Eqs. (19) and (6) in Eq. (16), and solving the resulting equation for all states, one can find the LQT ARE as

$$\bar{\mathbf{Q}} - \mathbf{P} + \gamma \bar{\mathbf{A}}^\top \mathbf{P} \bar{\mathbf{A}} - \gamma^2 \bar{\mathbf{A}}^\top \mathbf{P} \bar{\mathbf{B}} (\mathbf{R} + \gamma \bar{\mathbf{B}}^\top \mathbf{P} \bar{\mathbf{B}})^{-1} \bar{\mathbf{B}}^\top \mathbf{P} \bar{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{0}. \quad (20)$$

Remark 1. The presented LQT formulation using the Bellman principle is designed in the same format as the LQT presented in Kiumarsi et al. (2014), with the difference that, herein, an additional state is included to solve the steady-state error issue. Therefore, differently from Kiumarsi et al. (2014), the condition of a small discount factor or great tuning weight Q_0 is discarded since an integrator state, from the incremental form of the inputs, can guarantee the convergence of the tracking error to zero.

Remark 2. The LQT solution does not consider a Hurwitz criteria for \mathbf{F} as the discount factor is smaller than one (Kiumarsi et al., 2014). Therefore, in the proposed algorithm, for instance, an unit step reference change can be imposed as output trajectory.

Remark 3. As the presented solution follows the same form of that proposed in Kiumarsi et al. (2014), the Stability and Optimality of the LQT ARE solution still holds. Moreover, the algorithms for the Value Iteration and Policy Iteration can be replicated here, and, thus, the online RL algorithm can be obtained similarly.

3.2. Q-learning algorithm

The presented LQT problem can be solved by employing the RL algorithm in recursive iterations using the information of the system trajectories. Nevertheless, this resolution requires knowledge of the system dynamic, that is, the state-space matrices. Therefore, an alternative solution is to use the Q-learning method to exclude the necessity of the system's model. The Q (quality) function can be defined as a function of the states and control input, which in this case, is X and Δu , respectively. The Q-function is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} Q(\mathbf{X}_k, \Delta \mathbf{u}_k) &= \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{X}_k^\top \bar{\mathbf{Q}} \mathbf{X}_k + \Delta \mathbf{u}_k^\top \mathbf{R} \Delta \mathbf{u}_k + \gamma V(\mathbf{x}_{k+1})) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{X}_k^\top \bar{\mathbf{Q}} \mathbf{X}_k + \Delta \mathbf{u}_k^\top \mathbf{R} \Delta \mathbf{u}_k + \gamma \mathbf{X}_{k+1}^\top \mathbf{P} \mathbf{X}_{k+1}). \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Replacing the system dynamics in Eq. (21), the Q-function is rewritten in the matrix form

$$Q(\mathbf{X}_k, \Delta \mathbf{u}_k) = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}_k \\ \Delta \mathbf{u}_k \end{bmatrix} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{Q}} + \gamma \bar{\mathbf{A}}^\top \mathbf{P} \bar{\mathbf{A}} & \gamma \bar{\mathbf{A}}^\top \mathbf{P} \bar{\mathbf{B}} \\ \gamma \bar{\mathbf{B}}^\top \mathbf{P} \bar{\mathbf{A}} & \mathbf{R} + \gamma \bar{\mathbf{B}}^\top \mathbf{P} \bar{\mathbf{B}} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{W}} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}_k \\ \Delta \mathbf{u}_k \end{bmatrix}, \quad (22)$$

in which the kernel matrix $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}^\top$ can be resumed as

$$\mathbf{W} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W}_{XX} & \mathbf{W}_{X\Delta u_k} \\ \mathbf{W}_{\Delta u_k X} & \mathbf{W}_{\Delta u_k \Delta u_k} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (23)$$

Hence, following the same procedure for stationary condition of the LQT problem, one can define the optimal control law for the Q-function as

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial Q(\mathbf{X}_k, \Delta \mathbf{u}_k)}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{u}_k} &= 0, \\
\mathbf{W}_{XX} \mathbf{X}_k + \mathbf{W}_{\Delta \mathbf{u}_k \Delta \mathbf{u}_k} \Delta \mathbf{u}_k &= 0, \\
\Delta \mathbf{u}_k &= -\underbrace{(\mathbf{W}_{\Delta \mathbf{u}_k \Delta \mathbf{u}_k})^{-1}}_{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{W}_{XX} \mathbf{X}_k.
\end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

Notice that, to find the optimal control law \mathbf{K} , only the matrix \mathbf{W} is necessary. Therefore, RL method can be applied to determine the kernel matrix for the Q-learning problem.

With the goal to simplify the notation, consider the Kronecker product to write the Q-function

$$Q(\mathbf{X}_k, \Delta \mathbf{u}_k) = \overline{\mathbf{W}}^\top \overline{\mathbf{z}}_k, \tag{25}$$

in which $\overline{\mathbf{W}} = \text{vec}(\mathbf{W})$ is the format of matrix \mathbf{W} written as a vector, and $\overline{\mathbf{z}}_k = \mathbf{z}_k^\top \otimes \mathbf{z}_k$, for

$$\mathbf{z}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}_k \\ \Delta \mathbf{u}_k \end{bmatrix}. \tag{26}$$

Defining the value function at instant k as $r(\mathbf{X}_k, \Delta \mathbf{u}_k) = \mathbf{X}_k^\top \overline{\mathbf{Q}} \mathbf{X}_k + \Delta \mathbf{u}_k^\top \mathbf{R} \Delta \mathbf{u}_k$, the Bellman equation for the Q-function can be represented as

$$\overline{\mathbf{W}}^\top \overline{\mathbf{z}}_k = r(\mathbf{X}_k, \Delta \mathbf{u}_k) + \gamma \overline{\mathbf{W}}^\top \overline{\mathbf{z}}_{k+1}, \tag{27}$$

Therefore, taking into account the new Q-function Bellman equation (27), the policy iteration algorithm can be formulated for the learning of matrix $\overline{\mathbf{W}}^\top$ as follows

Remark 4. For the Policy Iteration, the Q-learning algorithm control law is dependent on the system states as $\Delta \mathbf{u}_k = -\mathbf{K} \mathbf{X}_k$, which means that for the LS algorithm in the Policy Improvement step, a persistence of excitation in the term $(\overline{\mathbf{z}}_k - \gamma \overline{\mathbf{z}}_{k+1})$ is required. Therefore, a probing signal must be added so that $\Delta \mathbf{u}_k = -\mathbf{K} \mathbf{X}_k + n_k$, in which n_k is defined as the dither. Notice that this condition does not affect the convergence of the Q-function estimation (Lewis and Vrabie, 2009).

Remark 5. To solve the policy evaluation step, one can choose the batch or the recursive LS method (Kiumarsi et al., 2014).

As can be noted, the proposed Q-learning algorithm can solve the LQT control problem with no knowledge of the system dynamics, using only the system state, system input, and output reference.

Algorithm 1 LQT Policy Iteration for the LQT Reinforcement Q-learning problem

Initialize. Start the algorithm selecting a stabilizing control law \mathbf{K} .

Policy Evaluation Step. Determine the value of \mathbf{W}_{j+1}^\top using a least square (LS) solution to

$$\overline{\mathbf{W}}_{j+1}^\top (\bar{\mathbf{z}}_k - \gamma \bar{\mathbf{z}}_{k+1}) = r(\mathbf{X}_k, \Delta \mathbf{u}_k). \quad (28)$$

Policy Improvement Step. Update the control law using the new calculate value of $\overline{\mathbf{W}}^\top$

$$\Delta \mathbf{u}_{k_{j+1}} = -((\mathbf{W}_{\Delta \mathbf{u}_k \Delta \mathbf{u}_k})_{j+1})^{-1} (\mathbf{W}_{XX})_{j+1} \mathbf{X}_k. \quad (29)$$

3.3. Numerical results

In this section, a simulation experiment is conducted to demonstrate the convergence and usefulness of the proposed Q-learning algorithm with the incremental form of the inputs. The solution presented previously is compared to the approach developed in Kiumarsi et al. (2014).

First, consider the following unstable system transfer function in the Laplace domain s

$$P(s) = \frac{0.5(s+1)}{-5s^2 + 2s + 10}. \quad (30)$$

In the sequence, the original state-space representation can be defined in discrete time as

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} x_{1_{k+1}} \\ x_{2_{k+1}} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} 5.388 & -1.492 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_{1_k} \\ x_{2_k} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0.5 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} u_k \\ y &= \begin{bmatrix} -0.472 & 0.182 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_{1_k} \\ x_{1_k} \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

The proposed Q-learning algorithm is employed considering two formulations: the incremental form of the input, as presented previously, and the standard form in Kiumarsi et al. (2014). In this simulation, a step response trajectory is imposed to the output reference. The discount factor is defined as $\gamma = 0.9$, the input weight tuning is set $R = 1$, and the persistent excitation dither is choosing as a random number with standard normal

distribution. For the sake of comparison, the Q-learning algorithm in incremental form is tuned with $Q_0 = 10$ and initiated with the control law $\mathbf{K}_{inc} = [10 \ -3 \ 0.85 \ 0.8]$. On the other hand, the standard formulation of the Q-learning algorithm uses three different tuning weights, $Q_0 = 10$, $Q_0 = 10^3$, and $Q_0 = 10^5$, and the initial control law $\mathbf{K}_{std} = [9 \ -1.5 \ 1]$. Notice that the dimension of \mathbf{K}_{inc} is defined according to the two system states, one input and one reference while the standard formulation does not consider the input values, and thus, has one less dimension. Both Q-Learning algorithms are solved using the batch LS resolution, considering the amount of samples $n_{batch} = 25$.

It is noteworthy that, in this simulated scenario, only the states and inputs of the proposed system is used to adapt the controllers' laws as no information about the system dynamics is required. Figure 3 depicts the simulation results for step change tracking scenario and Figs. 4 and 5 present the optimal gains of each proposed formulation. Noticed that, in Fig. 4, the three different adjusts of the standard formulation converges to the optimal gains after a short transient, and, as expected, greater gains magnitudes are achieved when using the tuning weight $Q_0 = 10^5$. Alike, in Fig. 4 is shown the Q-Learning algorithm in the incremental form also converges to optimal gains, but due to the action of the additional state related to the incremental input, the gains present less magnitudes. This comparison demonstrates that the standard form of the Q-Learning requires enormous values of Q_0 to minimize the steady-state error, while a small tuning weight is required for the incremental formulation.

Therefore, based on the demonstrated convergence and effectiveness of the Q-learning algorithm, the proposed optimal model-free controller is presented to control the SCF system of the CIESOL solar thermal plant.

4. Results

In this section, the Q-learning algorithm is employed to control the SCF using only the system measurements to achieve an optimal control law. The simulation is performed utilizing the CIESOL solar plant described in Section 2. In addition, the results consider the comparison of the proposed model-free strategy with the LQT controller under the same operational conditions. Therefore, actual meteorological and operational data of the CIESOL facility are used to replicate the scenarios for both controllers.

Figure 3: Comparison of the incremental and standard Q-learning algorithm for the reference tracking scenario.

Figure 4: Convergence of the Q-learning optimal gains for the standard formulation.

4.1. Convergence of the Q-learning for a nonlinear system

Firstly, aiming to demonstrate the applicability of the Q-learning method, a preliminary analysis is performed to evaluate the control performance and the convergence of the algorithm applied for regulating the nonlinear system.

Figure 5: Convergence of the Q-learning optimal gains for the incremental formulation.

For this aim, the nonlinear model of the SCF is used considering a hypothetical scenario in which the disturbance variables are kept constant, and step changes of the HTF output temperature reference are performed.

The stationary values of the disturbance variables are $\bar{I} = 447.15 \text{ W/m}^2$, $\bar{T}_a = 24.29 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and $\bar{T}_{sc,in} = 48.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which represents the irradiance, the ambient temperature, and the HTF inlet temperature, respectively. The controlled variable is HTF outlet temperature, in which the chosen calculated stationary value is $\bar{T}_{sc,o} = 59.75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Finally, the manipulated input is the HTF flow rate, with the stationary value $\bar{q} = 5 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$. In this simulation, no parameter variation is considered for the system model. For the algorithm tuning, the Q-learning parameters are chosen as $R = 1$, $Q_0 = 1$, $n_{batch} = 20$, and $\gamma = 0.9$. In addition, the batch LS method is chosen to solve the policy evaluation of the Reinforcement Q-learning, and the initial control law is defined as $\mathbf{K} = [0 \ 0 \ 0]$, which can be translated as leaving the system in open-loop.

Regarding the simulated scenario, two changes in the HTF output temperature are selected, altering the reference to $T_{ref} = 61 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and later to $T_{ref} = 58.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. These changes are imposed to observe the variation of the nonlinear model, which leads to different operating points of the system. The preliminary results are presented in Figs. 6 and 7. In Fig 6, it can be observed how the proposed algorithm can lead the system to the desired

references even when the controlled system is nonlinear. To evidence the convergence of the Q-learning algorithm, the optimal gains of the LQT strategy are computed offline, considering a linearized SCF model at each instant of the simulation (see Section Appendix B). As shown in Figure 7, the gains calculated by the model-free strategy converge to the optimal gains of the LQT. Furthermore, not only the Q-learning algorithm can control the nonlinear system, but it can also adapt the optimal gains as the system operating point changes, leading to an adaptive optimal control method, as expected.

Figure 6: Temperature control and HTF flow rate for the nonlinear SCF model simulation.

Based on the presented preliminary results, essential aspects must be considered before actual implementation. First of all, the tuning parameters of the Q-learning led to an abrupt change in the HTF flow rate, which could not be achieved in real scenarios. Moreover, the batch LS method can lead to a poor performance of the optimal gains adaptation since it recalculates the gains without considering the last computed solution, resulting in sudden changes in the gains. This issue is more evident in the nonlinear and multidisturbed systems, such as the SCF, since the optimal gains can vary considerably in short intervals of time. Notice that, in Fig. 7, differently from what happens in Figs. 4 and 5, when a reference change occurs, the control law is recalculated by the algorithm, which requires some time to converge to the new optimal gains. In addition, since the considered system is constantly disturbed, the probing noise is employed during the entire

Figure 7: Convergence of the Q-learning optimal gains for nonlinear SCF model simulation.

SCF operation to guarantee that the policy evaluation can keep adapting the control law at each instant regardless the reference changing. Therefore, these critical aspects are treated in the next section, focusing on achieving an effective and robust solution for controlling the SCF with the Q-learning algorithm.

4.2. Controlling the CIESOL SCF with Reinforcement Q-Learning

Aiming to represent a typical operation of the CIESOL facility, the primary circuit of the solar thermal plant depicted in Section 2 is employed in a trustworthy simulated scenario. The object of the experiment is to control the SCF system using the Q-learning algorithm in a closed circuit in charge of providing enough thermal energy to the load demand system, as presented in Fig. 2. For this purpose, actual data from the CIESOL facility on May 13, 2021, and May 14, 2021, are used to simulate a sunny day and a cloudy day operation, considering step changes in the HTF outlet temperature. As a result, the Q-learning algorithm faces typical operational situations such as reference tracking and output regulation. The control structure of the proposed adaptive optimal model-free strategy is represented in the block diagram in Fig. 8.

For the sake of comparison, the classical LQT optimal control is chosen as the benchmark control strategy to compare the Q-learning algorithm,

Figure 8: Block diagram scheme of the Q-Learning algorithm for the CIESOL SCF system.

since both strategies present the same control law and performance aspects. The LQT tuning is considered as $R = 10$ and $Q_0 = 1$, wherein the linear system model is computed considering the conditions of the beginning of the plant operation, that is, $\bar{T}_{sc,in} = 48.37$ °C, $\bar{T}_{sc,o} = 59.53$ °C, $\bar{q} = 5.02$ m³/h, and $H_n = 79.17$ J/(s·°C), leading to the following system gain $K_q = -2.17$ °C h/m³, time constant $\tau = 35.25$ s, and optimal gains $\mathbf{K}_{LQT} = [-0.1301 \ 0.0818 \ 0.120]$. Correspondingly, the Q-learning algorithm is also tuned with $R = 10$, $Q_0 = 1$, and $\gamma = 0.9$. Moreover, the sampling time for the gains adaptation is 60 sample periods and the initial gains is $\mathbf{K} = [0 \ 0 \ 0]$. Both controllers are implemented with a sample time of $t_s = 1$ s. In the simulated scenario, the actual plant limits are considered for the HTF flow rate, in which the minimum water flow is 2 m³/h, and the maximum is 15 m³/h.

With the focus on achieving a proper closed-loop behavior of the Q-learning algorithm for the SCF, minor modifications are considered for the control implementation. First, the batch LS algorithm is replaced by the recursive LS method to reduce the variations during the nonlinear system operation, as depicted in Fig. 7. The forgetting factor for the recursive LS is

chosen as $\gamma_{LS} = 0.9$. In addition, a low-pass filter is proposed for the reference signal to avoid sudden changes in the control inputs during reference tracking scenario. The filter tuning is set as 80% of the open-loop time constant of the system computed in a specific operating point, ($F_r = 1/(0.8\tau s + 1)$, for $\tau = 35.25$ s).

The results of the sunny day simulation are represented in Fig. 9. As can be seen, the Q-learning algorithm can properly control the SCF, tracking the reference along the entire operational period. On the other hand, the conventional LQT controller can control the plant only at the beginning, when the model used to compute optimal gains approximates the plant model. Along the plant operation, the nonlinearities and parameter model variations considerably alter the nominal model used at the beginning, generating a miss-match scenario in which the LQT cannot track the reference, resulting in an increasingly steady-state error.

To demonstrate the convergence of the Q-Learning algorithm, optimal gains are calculated offline considering the measurements of the plant (temperature, HTR flow and reference) during the system operation. The gains convergence is detailed in Fig. 10. Notice that the Q-Learning solution approximates the optimal gains even when the operating point of the SCF changes, which result in a model-free adaptive LQT solution. Moreover, from Fig. 10, one can note that the fixed LQT gains differ significantly from the gains calculated by the Q-learning strategy, which led to poor performance on controlling the SCF in reference tracking cases.

The second proposed scenario is detailed in Fig. 11, in which substantial variation in the irradiance occurs due to the cloudy day. Once again, the Q-learning algorithm can follow the reference adequately, differently from the conventional LQT, due to the same reasons regarding the gains adaptation, as depicted in Fig. 12. However, Q-learning algorithm performance is compromised in two specific moments. First, when the HTF flow is saturated at its low limit when the irradiance is critically reduced, and secondly, when strong disturbances affected the SCF. These scenarios led to an incorrect identification of the gains in the Q-learning algorithm at the policy evaluation stage, in which not optimal gains were used to control the system. Nevertheless, after the transient, the Q-learning algorithm returns to converge to the optimal gains and reestablishes the adequate control of the SCF. This can be noted in Fig. 12, where the Q-learning and the LQT gains are compared to the optimal gains computed offline for each operating point.

Aiming to quantitatively illustrate the convergence of the Q-learning al-

Figure 9: Temperature control and HTF flow rate for the nonlinear SCF model simulation.

Figure 10: Convergence of the Q-learning optimal gains for nonlinear SCF model simulation.

gorithm, the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) indices are calculated for the Q-learning, as defined in Eq. (32). The goal is to present the divergence from the optimal gains generated by the solution at each system operating point. As shown in Table 1, the

Q-learning algorithm presents less error in the sunny day scenario as small disturbance variations affect the SCF system.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MAE} &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^{k=N} |K_j(k) - K_{j_{adp}}(k)|, \\ \text{MAPE} &= \frac{100\%}{N} \sum_{k=1}^{k=N} \left| \frac{K_j(k) - K_{j_{adp}}(k)}{K_{j_{adp}}} \right|. \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

Table 1: MAE and MAPE indices for the optimal gains of Q-learning.

	Sunny day		Cloudy day		
	MAE [-]	MAPE [%]	MAE [-]	MAPE [%]	
Gains	K_x	0.011	9.77	0.016	14.27
	K_u	0.008	11.29	0.019	13.29
	K_r	0.009	14.64	0.015	28.87

Figure 11: Temperature control and HTF flow rate for the nonlinear SCF model simulation.

Finally, to demonstrate the effect of the time-varying parameter system, Fig. 13 depicts the variation of parameter H throughout the simulations in the sunny and cloudy scenarios. As can be seen, the parameter H of the

Figure 12: Convergence of the Q-learning optimal gains for nonlinear SCF model simulation.

nonlinear model substantially varies during the SCF operation, resulting from the difference between collectors' temperature and ambient temperature, as detailed in Eq. (1). Note that the quadratic error between the nominal model (considering a fixed parameter) and the actual model (considering a time-varying parameter) is higher when the parameter H is distanced from the nominal value $79.17 \text{ J}/(\text{s}\cdot^\circ\text{C})$.

4.3. Discussion

From the previously presented results, the proposed Q-learning algorithm model-free optimal adaptive controller is capable of adequately controlling the SCF system. As reviewed in Section 3, the algorithm dismisses the system model to present an optimal and adaptive control law attending to reference tracking and disturbance rejection scenarios. The advantages of the proposed model-free solution are evidenced in the simulated scenario. First, the Q-learning algorithm is simple to be implemented since the algorithm does not require any knowledge of the system, requiring only input/output measurements and the desired reference. This aspect can lead to a simple but powerful proposal for SCFs, since it can be extended to different systems effortlessly, assuming a minor understanding of the overall plant dynamic.

Furthermore, as observed in Fig. 13, the model parameter-varying and nonlinearity effect is irrelevant to the Q-learning algorithm since it considers

Figure 13: Variation of parameter H and quadratic error between the time-varying model ($H(T_{col})$) and constant model (H_n) during the simulated scenarios.

only the measurements of the inputs and outputs that already carry these contents. Even with frequent variations of the plant nonlinear dynamics, the model-free controller kept a satisfactory performance, as depicted in Figs. 9 and 11. These circumstances are particularly troubling to be treated by MBCs, such as an adaptive LQT solution, since several stages would be required to linearize the plant at each operating point, recalculate the optimal gains and readjust the controller.

Finally, crucial implementation aspects must be considered for the Q-learning algorithm. Concerning the solution of the policy evaluation, the variations of the calculated gains can be reduced by employing the recursive LS method, which is particularly important for the application in SCF as it presents high nonlinearities and is constantly disturbed. Regarding the disturbance variables, the LS method can perform poorly when strong disturbance and input/output saturation scenarios occur. When disturbance variables affect the output and are not considered in the RL algorithm, incorrect values of matrix $\overline{\mathbf{W}}$ (Eq. (28)) are computed, which corrupts the computation of the LQT gains using the RL method.

5. Final considerations

This work proposed an adaptive optimal model-free control for SCF systems. The solution is formulated considering the Reinforcement Q-Learning algorithm, in which an incremental form of the inputs is considered to solve the difficulty in tuning gains to eliminate steady-state error. The algorithm converges to optimal LQT gains, considering both linear systems, in which the gains are constants during the system evolution, and nonlinear systems, which are adapted when different operating change arises.

The model-free Q-learning method is employed to control the validated CIESOL thermal plant, considering a time-varying parameter model. The results demonstrate the advantages of the DDC compared to the conventional MBC LQT, in which the Q-learning can overcome the significant issues encountered by MBCs when controlling SCF, such as nonlinearities and parameter variations during the system operation. The results demonstrated that, for sunny day scenarios, the Q-Learning gains converge satisfactorily to the optimal gains, achieving less than 15% error during the proposed simulation. Moreover, the Q-learning algorithm shows to be very promising to be applied in different SCF, serving as a generic solution to control different solar systems submitted to different dynamics since this solution does not require the system models.

Further investigations must be addressed to improve the proposed Q-learning algorithm, such as disturbances variables, model delays, and input saturation, aiming to enhance the convergence and robustness of the solution. Moreover, the satisfactory simulated results encourage the implementation of the model-free strategy in the existing systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Igor M. L. Pataro: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - original draft, review and editing, Visualization. **Juan D. Gil:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - original draft, review and editing, Visualization. **José L. Guzmán:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review, Visualization. **Manuel Berenguel:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review, Visualization. **Rita Cunha:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review,

Visualization. **João M. Lemos:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review, Visualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Solar collector field model

The validated model used to simulate the SCF is presented as a simplified lumped-parameter dynamical model (Camacho et al., 2012). The validation results are shown in Pataro et al. (2022a). The nonlinear model equation is represented as

$$\begin{aligned} \rho C A_{sc} \frac{dT_{sc,o}(t)}{dt} = & \beta I(t) - \frac{H_n}{L_{eq}} (\bar{T}_{sc}(t) - T_a(t)) \\ & - \rho C q_{eq}(t) \frac{T_{sc,o}(t) - T_{sc,in}(t - d_{in})}{L_{eq}}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

in which

$$\begin{aligned} L_{eq} &= L \cdot n_{sc}, \\ \bar{T}_{sc}(t) &= \frac{T_{sc,o}(t) + T_{sc,in}(t)}{2}, \\ q_{eq}(t) &= \frac{q(t)}{c_f}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

The model parameters are β , H_n , A_{sc} , C , ρ , L_{eq} and c_f , which represent the irradiance efficiency factor, global heat losses coefficient, pipe cross-section area, specific heat capacity of the water, water density, equivalent absorber tube length, and the conversion factor, respectively. In addition, the disturbance variables are the HTF inlet temperature $T_{sc,in}(t)$ [°C], the solar irradiance $I(t)$ [W/m²], and the ambient temperature $T_a(t)$ [°C], while the manipulated variable is the water flow $q(t)$ [m³ /h]. The controlled variable of the represented system is the HTF outlet temperature $T_{sc,o}(t)$ [°C]. Finally, the transport delay $d_{T_{in}}$ is related to the inlet temperature. The model parameters are defined in Table A.2.

Table A.2: Model parameters description.

Parameter	Unit
A_{sc}	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-4}$ [m ²]
c_f	10·3600 [s/h]
C	4018 [J/(Kg·°C)]
H_n	79.17 [J/(s·°C)]
L	5.825 [m]
n_{sc}	8
β	0.432 [m]
ρ	1000 [Kg/m ³]

Appendix B. Linear model of the SCF

To calculate the optimal gains of the LQT controller, the nonlinear model described in (A.1) is linearized for an specified approximated equilibrium point. Consider the notation $\tilde{\mathbb{X}}(t) = \bar{\mathbb{X}} - \mathbb{X}(t)$, in which the chosen equilibrium point is $\bar{\mathbb{X}}$, and the deviation variable is defined as $\tilde{\mathbb{X}}(t)$. Hence, applying the Taylor series expansions only for the first derivative, the linearized model is synthesised as

$$\begin{aligned}
\underbrace{\left[\frac{\rho C A_{sc}}{c_f L_{eq}} + \frac{H_n}{2L_{eq}} \right]}_{\tau} \frac{d\check{T}_{sc,o}(t)}{dt} + \check{T}_{sc,o}(t) &= \underbrace{\left[\frac{\rho C \bar{q}}{c_f L_{eq}} + \frac{H_n}{2L_{eq}} \right]}_{K_I} \check{I}(t) \\
+ \underbrace{\left[\frac{\rho C \bar{q}}{c_f L_{eq}} + \frac{H_n}{2L_{eq}} \right]}_{K_{T_{in}}} \check{T}_{in}(t - d_{T_{in}}) &+ \underbrace{\left[\frac{\rho C \bar{q}}{c_f L_{eq}} + \frac{H_n}{2L_{eq}} \right]}_{K_{T_a}} \check{T}_a(t) + \underbrace{\frac{-\frac{C\rho}{c_f L_{eq}} (\bar{T}_{sc,o} - \bar{T}_{sc,in})}{\left[\frac{\rho C \bar{q}}{c_f L_{eq}} + \frac{H_n}{2L_{eq}} \right]}}_{K_q} \check{q}(t).
\end{aligned} \tag{B.1}$$

In possesses of the linear model, the Laplace transformation can be employed considering the input $\check{q}(t)$ and the output $\check{T}_{sc,o}(t)$, leading to the transfer functions representations as

$$\check{T}_{sc,o}(s) = \frac{K_q \check{q}(s)}{(\tau s + 1)} \tag{B.2}$$

This representation ca be used to formulate the nominal state-space matrices of the linear system, which is then applied to compute the LQT optimal gains.

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